

I.FAST

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MILESTONES REPORT

Performance of Superconductive Cavities made by AM technology by Nb or Cu with Nb thin spattered film on the internal surface

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the deliverable D10.4 was to assess the manufacturability of seamless SRF cavities made of copper or/and niobium by Additive Manufacturing technology. In particular, the employed technique is Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF).

The effectiveness of the process was successfully demonstrated both for copper and niobium. After intense studies for the evaluation of process parameters, the SRF cavities were produced. Surface treatments were performed in order to reduce the surface roughness of the AMed parts to achieve the surface roughness target value of 1 μm .

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The aim of the deliverable D10.4 was to assess the manufacturability of seamless SRF cavities made of copper or/and niobium by Additive Manufacturing technology. In particular, the employed technique is Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF).

The effectiveness of the process was successfully demonstrated both for copper and niobium. After intense studies for the evaluation of process parameters, the SRF cavities were produced. Surface treatments were performed in order to reduce the surface roughness of the AMed parts to achieve the surface roughness target value of 1 μm .

1. Objectives

Explored effectiveness of AM to produce RF cavities in pure Copper with roughness under 1 μm of the inner surface, printing samples and assessing surface treatments (both mechanical and chemical) in preparation for using pure Niobium.

2. Description of the previous work (Deliverable)

The aim of Task 10.4 is to evaluate the reliability of AM as manufacturing technique to produce seamless 6 GHz superconducting cavities. Initial copper prints were done at DIAM (INFN – Padua Division). Half cavities were initially printed to evaluate different printing parameters and building direction (three horizontal halves, three vertical halves, and three complete cavities, printed vertically, see Fig. 1 a). Furthermore, the printability of such geometry was tested without using internal supports, since they would be detrimental for the surface finish and extremely difficult to remove. Then three complete cavities were printed without internal supports and provided with flanges at the extremities to perform leak tests and cryogenic tests (Fig. 1 b). A fourth half cavity (printed vertically) was also printed.

Pieces were then shipped to Rösler Italiana S.r.l., which performed the surface treatments: two out of four halves were subjected to mechanical treatments, while the other two were treated with chemical-assisted mechanical treatments. The roughness of the down-skin region and material loss was measured after each treatment step. Once the Ra value achieved was less than 1 μm , the specimens were shipped to INFN-LNL to be treated with SUBU5 (chemical polishing) and Electropolishing. Specimens were finally shipped at INFN – Padua Division and CMM analyses have been performed on each sample (Fig. 1 c). The measurements allowed comparing the real final geometry of the half cavities treated with the initial CAD geometry (Fig. 1 d). In such a way, the material loss due to the treatments was estimated.

Meanwhile, two copper cavities were printed by a company with a 515 nm wavelength green laser (Fig. 1 e), and other three copper cavities were printed at DIAM Laboratory (Fig. 1 f).

Figure 1: a) first print; b) flanged cavities; c) measurements performed with Zeiss Accura CMM facility; d) profiles obtained by the geometry measurements; e) full-length 6 GHz cavity prototype printed with green laser; f) full-length 6 GHz cavity prototypes printed at DIAM Laboratory (INFN-Padova).

Concerning niobium, samples were printed with different process parameters (Fig. 2 a), and densities were measured by Archimedes' method. Currently, the maximum relative density achieved is equal to 99.87 %. The printability of self-supporting inclined walls (Fig. 2 b) was also assessed, to determine the limit angle of pure niobium. Walls inclined with different angles were created, from a maximum angle of 50° to a minimum angle of 18°. From the first trial, only walls having angles higher than 35° were successfully printed, the other walls failed.

Figure 2: a) Samples for density estimation; b) inclined walls.

Despite the positive results on the preparatory work, Task 10.4 has experienced considerable delays related to slow reaction of companies during the Covid-19 pandemic and to the shortage of base materials, with increase in price. The copper powders for printing were received late, and the low-contamination niobium powders for final printing were not yet received. The consequence is that one Deliverable and one Milestone have to be delayed.

In the period between May and October 2022 the research was mainly focused on LPBF of pure niobium. Further trials have been performed: several printing tests were carried out with the aim of improving the downward-facing surface quality. Down-skin and contour parameters were studied in deep, and innovative contactless supporting structures were developed. The only use of optimized parameters did not allow to reach overhang surfaces having angles lower than 30°. By using contactless supports, it was possible to go below this limiting angle, and at the same time, the surface roughness was considerably decreased. Thanks to these innovative structures, three pure niobium 6 GHz cavities were successfully printed: one cavity having a height of 50 mm and two cavities 88 mm high (Fig. 3).

3.

Figure 3: Pure niobium 6 GHz SRF cavities produced via LPBF at DIAM laboratory: a) 50 mm high Nb cavity; b) 88 mm high Nb cavity.

Leak tests and RF measurements were carried out for two of the Nb cavities produced (that 50 mm high and one of the two with the height of 88 mm): the tightness revealed to be excellent and a leak rate $<10^{-12}$ mbar*s was successfully. The frequency was measured at room temperature and in as-built conditions: the results are reported in Table 1. A T_c of 9.2 K (identical to bulk Nb) was measured on a small sample of Nb by inductive method.

Internal inspection showed that the as-built surface quality is good inside the cell and the use of contactless supports guarantees a homogeneous internal surface roughness.

Table 1 Frequency of the niobium cavities produced via LPBF (as built).

Cavity	Frequency [GHz]
50 mm	5.999
88 mm	6.027

Concerning the copper cavities, there are 8 prototypes up to now (2 full-length cavities printed with the green laser, indicated as T1 and T2 in the following Table 2, three full-length cavities, indicated as L1, L2, and L3, and three flanged cavities, indicated with P1, P2, and P3 abbreviations). Before any treatment, the resonant frequency was measured at room temperature and data are available in

Table 1. Internal inspection was carried out, too, and images of cut-off, iris, and equatorial regions were taken. These prototypes were subjected to the same surface treatments developed by Rösler Italiana S.r.l. mentioned above. The target surface roughness (Ra) value of 1 μm has not been achieved yet.

Table 2: Frequency of the printed copper cavities at room temperature, in as-built conditions.

Cavity	Frequency [GHz]
T1	5.9871875
T2	5.986250
L1	5.9956250
L2	6.0015625
L3	6.0043750
P1	5.9481250
P2	5.9418750
P3	5.9390625

The printability of copper and niobium seamless 6GHz SRF cavities has been proven, Additive Manufacturing (and specifically Laser Powder Bed Fusion technology) is a suitable technique for their production. Concerning the niobium cavities, three seamless cavities have been successfully produced and the internal inspection and resonant frequency measurement have been conducted. The Deliverable has been satisfied.

3. Milestones

Milestone MS46: Performance of Superconductive Cavities made by AM technology by Nb or Cu with Nb thin spattered film on the internal surface – DELAYED to M30

Some of the copper cavities are ready to proceed with the internal Nb sputtering, while the remaining ones are completing the surface treatments stage. The tightness and the resonant frequency in as-built conditions have been checked, in addition, an internal inspection has been conducted (see figures 4,5,7,8) to assess the surface quality after printing; other tests to evaluate the performance of the specimens will be done in the next months.

Surface treatments

The copper cavities, particularly T1 and T2, underwent mass-transfer mechanical polishing treatments by Rösler Italiana S.r.l. Subsequently, they underwent a series of surface treatments at the Legnaro National Laboratories (LNL) of INFN. The standard protocol for bulk copper cavities involves vibro-tumbling polishing, electrochemical polishing, chemical polishing in SUBU solution, passivation, and final High-Pressure Rinsing (HPR) steps. For additively manufactured structures, additional optimizations and adjustments are necessary to achieve a target surface roughness (Ra) value of $< 1 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4: internal surface quality during major steps of vibro-tumbling (VT) and electropolishing (EP) for T1 copper cavity

Figure 5: internal surface quality after production and electropolishing (EP) for T2 copper cavity

During the surface treatments, both T1 and T2 cavities experienced leaks (in the case of T1, rupture, see figure 6). Consequently, none of the copper cavity can be evaluated in terms of superconductivity performance. No sputtering of the superconductive (SC) layer has been done yet. Further optimization of printing parameters, along with reinforcements, is expected in the near future to enable successful surface preparation before SC deposition via magnetron deposition and finally RF measurement.

Figure 6: leak and rupture in the iris position of the T1 and T2 copper cavities respectively

Regarding the Niobium bulk cavities, three resonators were treated at the LNL of INFN. The 55 mm height sample (Nb0) served as a benchmark to assess the structure's ability to withstand mechanical load during vibro-tumbling. Following three different time intervals (60, 150, and 180 minutes), the cavity underwent extensive mass-transport mechanical polishing. Internal inspection of the surface preliminarily revealed the success of the internal polishing, allowing the next steps for cavities of 88 mm height.

Both cavities underwent similar treatments, starting with long vibro-tumbling polishing (Nb2: 180 min, 300 min, 24 h; Nb1: 120 min, 90 min, respectively). After vibro-tumbling, a series of electropolishing steps were applied, resulting in 21 g removal (around 400 μm) in the case of the Nb2 cavity. Similarly, the Nb1 cavity underwent two steps of electropolishing (125–150 μm average thickness removed). A summary of the treatments is described below in table 4.

Figure 7: internal surface quality after major steps of vibro-tumbling (VT) and electropolishing (EP) for niobium Nb2 cavity

Figure 8: internal surface quality after major steps of vibro-tumbling (VT) and electropolishing (EP) for niobium Nb1 cavity

Table 3: Summary of the surface treatments workflow conducted on printed cavities.

Treatment details	copper T1	copper T2	niobium Nb2	niobium Nb1
Mass-finishing @ Rösler Italiana S.r.l.	✓	✓	✗	✗
Vibro-tumbling @ LNL-INFN	✗	✗	VT1: 120 min; 13 µm	VT1: 180 min; 15 µm
			VT2: 90 min; 6 µm	VT2: 300 min; 12 µm
			✗	VT3: 24h min; 18 µm
Electropolishing @ LNL-INFN	EP1: 80 min; 116 µm	EP1*: 70 min; 92 µm	EP1: 45 min; 55 µm	EP1: 60 min; 90 µm
	EP2: 67 min; 105 µm	✗	EP2: 45 min; 70 µm	EP2: 90 min; 150 µm
	✗	✗	✗	EP3: 90 min; 150 µm
Vibro-tumbling @ LNL-INFN	VT1: 60 min; 15 µm	✗	✗	✗
	VT2*: 35 min; 23 µm			

Total average thickness removed	259 μm	92 μm	144 μm	445 μm
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Performance evaluation

All Nb cavities successfully passed leak detection tests (conducted after each mechanical and chemical treatment step), indicating that Ultra High Vacuum conditions can be achieved inside the cavities.

For the liquid He leak test, cavity Nb2 was assembled in the cryostat and underwent cooling. Unfortunately, the cavity presented a leak, rupturing at about 20 K during liquid He transfer (see figure 9). For this cavity, only the frequency after the chemical treatments was obtained (at room temperature) – 5.995 GHz.

Figure 9: rupture of the niobium cavity Nb2 in the iris position

In the case of Nb1 cavity, initial measurements were taken (see figure 10) prior to any treatment (in the as-printed state). The resonant frequency at room temperature was 6.040 GHz. Q_{loaded} at zero field was measured with a network analyzer at 4.2 K, resulting in $Q \approx 1,36 \cdot 10^5$. After a series of treatments, the resonant frequency was measured again: at room temperature – 6.014 GHz and at 4.2 K – 6.025 GHz. Unfortunately, due to the limitation of the present signal generator (max 6.0000 GHz), cavities that exceed this limit cannot be measured. Thus, after surface preparation at 4.2 K, only Q_{loaded} at zero field was measured $Q \approx 5,03 \cdot 10^5$.

Figure 10: network analyzer test of Q_{loaded} of the niobium Nb1 cavity at 4.2 K before (left) and after (right) treatments

The performance improvement is approximately five times better than as-printed, but still much lower than 6 GHz spun cavities ($Q \approx 2 \cdot 10^7$). The obtained results are most likely determined by the final surface quality (especially macro and micro roughness, presence of pitting and other defects, cleanliness of the material, and final density). As the risks of ruptures, cracks, and other failures are relatively high (examples are both Cu and Nb cavities that appeared during surface treatments stage or even during the liquid He transfer), additional reinforcement structures are suggested to be added. Moreover, optimization studies of the quantity of material removal are needed to understand the minimum average surface thickness removal and maximum values (to avoid the above-described issues). Heat treatments (in particular annealing) can as well contribute to the final performance, as in the standard protocols are normally applied. A slight modification of cavity design has to be applied to avoid extensive need for internal material removal to lower the cavity resonant frequency below the 6.0 GHz value in compliance with the signal generator. Additionally, optimization of printing parameters can potentially improve the down-skin region quality, thus enhancing the final RF performance.

4. Future Activities

In order to validate the effectiveness of the design modifications in the failure-prone regions of the components (specifically, the transition zone between IRIS and Cut-off), new SRF Cavities will be manufactured using the LPBF process in both Niobium (Nb) and Copper (Cu). These cavities will undergo chemical treatment to minimize surface roughness, followed by comprehensive testing to ascertain the tangible enhancement in their resistance. The additional proposed activities will be delineated into three distinct phases: refinement of the external design for SRF Nb and Cu cavities; optimization of the downskin surface to ensure the production of pure copper utilizing a 1 kW red laser system; and, lastly, surface enhancement coupled with SRF performance testing (with confirmation of the availability of resources from both Rösler Italiana S.r.l. and the Legnaro National Laboratories of INFN). No additional budgetary allocations will be necessary for the execution of these tasks. In the following paragraphs, these new additional activities will be explained in depth:

- **Refinement of the External Design for SRF Niobium and Copper Cavities**

To prevent the occurrence of breakage in SRF cavities during testing, alterations were made to the external design at the transition zone between IRIS and Cut-off. The concept of reinforcing the critical area is depicted in Figure 11, showcasing the approach of strengthening without compromising the internal geometry crucial for the proper functionality of the SRF cavity.

Figure 11: representation of the strengthening of the external transition zone between IRIS and Cut-off of the SRF cavity

- **Enhancing Downskin Surface Optimization in Pure Copper through Additive Manufacturing with LPBF Systems Featuring a 1kW Red Laser**

The research activity investigated the influence of different downskin parameters on surface quality at inclination angles lower than 20° .

Some samples were created processing a copper powder with an AMCM-customized machine M290, provided with 1kW IR-laser.

Some downskin parameters combinations were investigated: 6 samples with the same infill parameters were built, the geometry can be seen in fig. 12a and b.

Figure 12: a) section of the sample used for the study; b) perspective view of the sample.

Samples were conceived to investigate the printability of unsupported overhanged structures with a minimum inclination of 18° with respect to the horizontal plane.

In addition, the geometry was created inserting a fillet to check the quality of the part, since the difficulty in obtaining good results for downskin fillets is known. Indeed, from our prior tests carried out at DIAM (INFN-Padova) and cavity prototypes printed by an external company, we saw that the upper iris region is the weakest point for mechanical resistance and tightness, if the building process is not specifically optimized.

These samples were printed without using supporting structures.

3 out of 6 samples were considered good and examined: 1, 2 and 6 (all the samples are visible in Figure 13).

Figure 13: Samples built with the infill parameters, but different downskin. Sample 4 was deactivated during the printing process for overheating.

For samples 1, 2 and 6, optical roughness estimation was carried out: samples 1 and 2 showed a lower S_a than sample 6: $79.7 \mu\text{m}$, $70.1 \mu\text{m}$ and $95.7 \mu\text{m}$, respectively.

Samples were then mounted, and their cross-section examined at OM (Figure 14).

Figure 14: cross-section of the samples at OM.

From Figure 14 Sample 1 and 2 showed a thickness reduction in the upper part, while in sample 6 the CAD characteristics seemed better preserved.

Further investigations are needed before printing real prototypes for reducing the porosity and avoiding heavy thickened reduction.

Some full-length 6 GHz SRF copper cavities are going to be built after further tests on downskin. A new design is foreseen to minimize the risks of a premature failure during post processing (internal surface treatments) in correspondence of iris regions.

5. Acknowledgments

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